

Extending the lifetime of journal bearings for high-speed trains

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Abstract

The research described in this paper addresses a particular rolling stock component for high-speed-rail applications: the journal (or axlebox) bearing, which is the one of the topics of the GEARBODIES research project. The paper summarises the first three phases of the project: 1. terms of reference, requirements and specifications, 2. assessment and selection of technology concepts, 3. development through investigations and lab testing. After the final validation phase, the work-plan will lead to the proposal of low Life-Cycle Cost (LCC) bearing Design Concepts for the high-speed trains of the future, with a focus on extra- and ultra-long bearing lifetime. In the paper, the identified lifetime targets and the selection of the technology concepts are described. Some key technologies investigated in the project are then discussed. Firstly, High Entropy Alloys (HEA), for the bearing components in rolling contact, show huge potential due to the unprecedentedly vast possibility of fine-tuning their properties by varying their composition. Secondly, polymer/lubricant combinations are being investigated, with a focus on the ageing properties of polymer bearing cages for ultra-long lifetime. Thirdly, lubrication solutions, with a focus on oil lubrication as a promising technology concept to obtain the long-lasting extremely low frictional dissipation required for long lifetime.

Keywords: journal bearing, High Entropy Alloys (HEA), polymers, lubrication

1. Introduction

The research described in this paper addresses a particular rolling stock component for high-speed-rail applications: the journal (or axlebox) bearing, which is one of the topics of the 25-month GEARBODIES project [1].

A significant bearing lifetime extension – from today's 1.6-1.7 million kilometres (Mkm) and around 4 years, at best, to over 10 Mkm and 25 years (SHIFT2RAIL vision) – would be key in reducing the number of costly overhauls required by the railway vehicle over its lifetime.

Therefore, the research carried out within GEARBODIES is focussing on three areas for extending the bearing lifetime (see Figure 1):

- A. use of novel materials (for rollers, races, rings and cages);
- B. lubrication solutions; and
- C. optimised design (including optimised component geometry and integration on the bogie).

GEARBODIES aims to develop and validate Design Concepts (DCs) for journal bearings with extended lifetime to be used on high-speed trains. The work comprises four phases:

1. terms of reference, requirements and specifications;
2. assessment and selection of technology concepts;
3. development of innovative journal bearing elements with enhanced performance;
4. evaluation and validation of concepts.

The main expected results are the DCs, which will be evaluated and partly validated. One concept – the “focussed DC” – will be manufactured as a prototype, tested and documented. The “open DCs” will be validated at lower TRL, through modelling, simulation and laboratory tests, in view of further development.

This paper describes the intermediate results regarding the process leading to the definition of the DCs and the preliminary findings of the investigations leading to the laboratory testing (items 1, 2, and 3 of the list above).

Figure 1: Scope and concept of the GEARBODIES project funded by Shift2Rail.

2. Terms of reference, requirements and specifications

The findings of the first GEARBODIES phase led to the definition of user requirements and specifications (technology concepts, materials, geometry etc.) for the focussed and open DCs [2]. As described therein, detailed targets for the bearing unit lifetime (Table 1) for SHIFT2RAIL’s System Platform Demonstrator SPD1 “high speed” have been defined according to the SHIFT2RAIL vision. Two stages of advancement were set: extra-long lifetime – for the focussed DC – and ultra-long lifetime – for the open DCs. The latter corresponds to an overall unit lifetime of 25 years made up of two equal maintenance intervals.

It was argued that approximately doubling today’s maintenance interval to about 3 Mkm (extra-long lifetime) should not lead to roller/ring fatigue problems emerging if state-of-the-art steels are used. However, the generated frictional power needs to be further reduced with respect to state-of-the-art bearing designs, to prolong lubricant life which is the main limiting factor today. Extending the lifetime further, even with ultra-low friction and perfect sealing to preserve the lubricant, could see the roller and ring fatigue problem re-emerging, potentially requiring novel materials. Moreover, the ultra-long-term ageing behaviour of the current and upcoming polymeric cage materials interacting with lubricants is unknown and requires further research.

Component maintenance interval	Current (C)		Extra-Long-lifetime XL			Ultra-Long-lifetime UL		
	Mkm	yrs	Mkm	yrs	Δ% C	Mkm	yrs	Δ% C
Lubricant	1.65	3.7	3.0	6.7	+82%	5.625	12.5	+241%
Cage	1.65	3.7	3.0	6.7	+82%	5.625	12.5	+241%
Seals	1.65	3.7	3.0	6.7	+82%	5.625	12.5	+241%

annual running distance of 0,45 Mkm (SPD1 high-speed)

Table 1: Definition of lifetime targets.

3. Assessment and selection of technology concepts

The technology concepts shortlisted in the first phase as promising for extra-long and ultra-long lifetime (Table 2) were further assessed and narrowed down in the second phase.

Open concepts (TRL3-4)	
Target ultra-long maintenance interval: 5.625 Mkm	
Target ultra-long lifetime: Up to 11.25 Mkm (2 maintenance intervals, 25 years at 0.45 Mkm/year SPD1)	
Rollers	Open: balls, cylinders, tapered
Layout	Open: Twin-tandem [®] , conventional cylindrical, conventional tapered
Lubricant / lubrication concept	SOA grease or oil, novel oil lubrication concept
Roller material	Novel HEA or HEA coated
Ring material	Novel HEA or HEA coated
Cage material	novel polymeric material based on PA or PEEK
Sealing	SOA cartridge seals
Running gear configurations	Conventional high-speed bogie layout and/or in-board-bearing configuration

Table 2: Options shortlisted for the “open Design Concepts”

A structured approach based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [3] was used for the assessment and further selection of the most promising solutions. Four main specific objectives were identified, contributing to the main goal of journal bearing Life-Cycle Cost (LCC) reduction:

- improvement of lubricant lifetime;
- improvement of lifetime of components in rolling contact;
- Improvement of lifetime of cages;
- other LCC impacts.

For each objective, specific criteria were identified. For example, for lubricant lifetime:

- reducing frictional power by acting on the overall surface in contact, shear stresses, micro-slip etc.,
- minimising contaminant particles (including e.g., minimising the generation of wear particles, and removing contaminant particles in service but excluding the ingress of contaminants through the seals which is out of the project’s scope);
- provision of the possibility for lubricant replacement without disassembling the bearing.

For the lifetime of the components in rolling contact, the increase of the Hardness/Elastic modulus ratio for better wear and fatigue resistance and the improvement /increase of phase stability (by reducing diffusion coefficients) for better ultra-long duration fatigue resistance were identified among the key criteria.

For the lifetime of cages, the optimisation of polymer/lubricant combination for the best mechanical properties after ageing was identified as the key criterion.

The other LCC impacts considered are the reduction of component cost/price, reduction in implementation difficulty (regulatory and standardisation barriers, etc.), reduction of running gear maintenance costs, reduction in other operation costs (aerodynamic resistance, unsprung mass etc.), reduction of end-of-life costs.

4. Development of innovative journal bearing elements

4.1 Novel materials for rollers and rings: High Entropy Alloys (HEA)

As opposed to conventional alloys, which are composed of one principal element (such as iron for steel alloys) with secondary elements in much lower concentrations, HEA involve 4 or more principal elements, all in relatively high concentrations [2]. The large number of element combinations implies an enormous number of

possible systems and the freedom to tune compositions to achieve desired mechanical properties. HEA are thus a promising solution for the development of highly wear-resistant and low friction rollers and rings. As the second phase of the project already confirmed the extremely high interest in their potential, HEAs are a key focus of the third phase of GEARBODIES, i.e., development of relevant samples and laboratory testing. The rolling contact fatigue in bearing components may lead to phase transformations (e.g., dark etching regions (DER) and white etching bands (WEB), which are an indication of microstructural instability (martensite decay). Possible solutions for this degradation phenomenon are hard coatings (TiN, TiC, TiCN, AlN, WC) and HEAs, which could be used either as base material or coating. In phase 2 of the project, it was decided to focus on HEAs used as a coating, as a more cost-efficient solution. HEAs tend to form solid solutions due to their high configurational entropy, leading to “sluggish diffusion” and thus could provide good phase stability.

The investigations carried out through modelling and simulation allowed for a pre-selection of the most promising compositions, based on Hume-Rothery (HR) rules [4] e.g., similar valency and electronegativity. A Fortran code was developed and used for assessing 4, 5 and 6 element alloys based on HR rules from all elements in the periodic table, which resulted into 39 candidate alloys (11 four element alloys, 21 five element alloys, 7 six element alloys (Figure 2). The pre-selection was further narrowed down to 4 alloys by applying additional criteria to the predicted elastic (elasticity moduli) and plastic properties (hardness, plasticity index) of the alloys, using DFT (Density Functional Theory) [5] and empirical relationships. For example, the elasticity modulus for an alloy used as a coating for steel (Figure 2) should be in the same range as that of the base steel to avoid poor bonding between the materials.

Figure 2: Example assessment of potential HEAs: Young’s elasticity modulus for the pre-selected alloys, as calculated with Discrete Functional Theory

Further research will be carried out in the project for the investigation and validation of selected alloys, comprising:

- fabrication of samples through specific processes, e.g.:
 - mechanical alloying: the selected elementary powders are mixed through high energy milling to obtain each selected alloyed powder, whose properties are confirmed with the X-Ray powder diffraction technique [6];
 - coating of steel discs with the alloyed powder;
- laboratory testing, including:
 - metallographic analysis of the coatings;
 - hardness measurements;

- tribological testing;
- comparison of the behaviour of the novel materials with the predicted behaviour (from modelling) and the behaviour of the benchmark materials (steel grades).

Based on the test results, one or more HEAs will be recommended (as open DC) for the journal bearing components in rolling contact.

4.2 Novel polymer/lubricant combinations

Although subjected to lower loads, the polymeric materials widely used for bearing cages will have to stand the test of time and temperature for ultra-long lifetime. The conventional polyamides (PA) and more novel poly-ether-ether-ketones (PEEK) are expected to achieve this objective, in combination with state-of-the-art lubricants (both grease and oil). However, this needs to be ascertained and eventual improvements suggested through specific research.

For this purpose, samples and specimens based on the materials and lubricants selected in the previous project phase are being manufactured and tested. In particular, the effect of the lubricant on the ageing of the polymers (swelling and oxidation of the materials) is of interest.

The polymers selected for the tests are a commercial PA66 reinforced with glass fibre (33%) and a novel PEEK solution not employed for journal bearings yet. Samples are being manufactured by injection moulding, according to the norm ASTM D790, which recommends the geometry for subsequent mechanical tests. For the lubricants, a solid lubricant (grease) approved in at least two EU countries for high-speed trains and a liquid lubricant (oil) have been chosen. The latter, seldom used in recent decades, is of interest due to the interesting potential of oil lubrication for ultra-long lifetime identified in the previous project phases.

The key tests to which the samples are being subjected have been designed based on the relevant tests in standards (the “thermal ageing in grease or oil bath” specified in EN 12080 [7] and the “immersion test” specified in ASTM D543 [8]). A part of the samples prepared is being subjected to accelerated ageing at 140°C in autoclave with the appropriate lubricant bath. They will be subjected to tensile tests, 3-point bending tests (e.g., to determine mechanical property changes such as fracture strength loss after 250 h and 500 h of ageing of the aged samples). A total of 180 samples (45 samples per test and per polymer) are being used.

After the mechanical tests, the remaining material will be used for microstructural and tribological measurements (structural characterization, optical and SEM microscopy, tribology characterization).

The results will inform the choices for journal bearing cages (as open Design Concepts).

4.3 Lubrication solutions

Following on from the findings of the previous project phases, the development work on lubrication solutions looked more closely at the suitability of oil as a lubricant. In the assessment phase, it was found that the use of oil could offer several advantages, such as:

- easy maintenance (oil change without disassembly of the bearings);
- longevity of the lubricant;
- good potential for removal of contaminants;
- contacts are well supplied with lubricant;
- the system can be further expanded (e.g., with an oil cooling system, a single oil supply to wheelset bearing and gearbox, etc.).

Besides the advantages, there is also a big challenge for this solution. The system must be 100% sealed to the environment, because oil leakage is not acceptable. There are two options for sealing the system: sealing directly on the bearing (Figure 3a) or designing a new housing including seals (Figure 3b).

Both possibilities were extensively investigated, both theoretically (housing with sealing) and practically in tests (bearing sealing against oil leakage). In the tests, the wheelset bearings were filled with oil (different fill levels) and the sealings were tested for leaks. It was found that 100 % sealing against oil leakage cannot be guaranteed. The same applies to the housing solution. Most of the oil can be guided away from the seals by the internal design, but there is a great risk that the oil that is in contact with the seals will leak out. New seal development would be necessary here, which is not being pursued as part of the project. The findings will be used to influence the open Design Concepts at the end of the project.

(a) Sealed Bearing

(b) New housing with sealings

Figure 3: sealing of oil-lubricated bearings

5. Conclusions

At the time of writing, the GEARBODIES research project is around the half-way mark. Thus far, requirements and high-level specifications for the journal bearing Design Concepts have been drafted, including lifetime targets, the technology concepts to be further developed have been assessed and selected, and further investigations and laboratory testing are being performed on the selected High Entropy Alloys and polymer/lubricant combinations, as well as for the novel lubrication solutions and component designs. The next steps are the formulation and validation of the Design Concepts.

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